

BAMBOO

D2.5: Definition of specifications and data requirements for waste streams valorisation as fuels analysis

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BAMBOO

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document analyzes the most relevant waste streams with a potential interest to be used as fuel in the demo-sites of AMIII, UPM and TÜPRAS. The most important parameters, like the composition, heating values or availability at each demo-site are explained, together with the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of these fuels in order to be valorized on site.

2 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The processes of the energy intensive industries like steel, paper and petrochemical generate some waste streams which can be valorised as fuels and, consequently, can contribute to reduce the energy consumption and the pollutant emissions of these industries. For the mineral sector, there is not a generation of internal waste streams that can be valorised as fuels, so that external waste streams (including agroindustrial biomass and forestry residues) are proposed as flexibility vectors and evaluated in the framework of Task 2.4.

In the case of the steel sector, the gases generated from the cokemaking (coke oven gas), from the steelmaking (converter gas) and from the ironmaking (blast furnace gas) present a calorific value which makes them potential substitutes of the natural gas uses in the different furnaces. They can also be used to generate steam onsite, reducing the operational cost. However, the use of these gases involves some drawbacks which limit their use in terms of flexibility.

For AMIII, the configuration of the plants of Gijón and Avilés limits the use of the off-gases to the own plant where they are generated. The scope of their contribution is the reduction of the natural gas consumption, but their use requires not only economic investment, but some combustion constraints to be solved. The objective of this document is to carry out a complete characterization of these gases and to analyse the advantages and disadvantages of their use for other processes in AMIII. These data will be the input for WP5 where novel strategies for combustion monitoring will be developed, and for WP6 related to the flexibility tool.

Regarding the paper sector, the analysis focuses on the residual streams generated within the Plattling mill site. Three types of sludge residuals have been identified, coming from the purification process of the wastewater, before its discharge to the Isar river: primary sludge, bio sludge and deinking sludge, whose main characteristics are presented.

The aim of the project in UPM is the reduction of the moisture content in the bio sludge, in order to improve its heating value and use it as fuel. In this case, the dried sludge will be sold to the market or used as fuel in another UPM paper mill. In WP5, CFD simulations will be carried out in order to characterize the combustion behaviour of the bio-sludge and determine optimum substitution rates to couple the operation of the boiler and sludge drier. Other valorisation routes will be also analysed during the project.

About the petrochemical sector, most of the refineries off-gases and flare recovery gases are currently valorised in Tüpras refineries, so there are no big chances of flexibility. However, the refinery fuel gases contain an important amount of hydrogen and offer potential alternative uses when the recovery processes become feasible.

3 METHODOLOGY

For the elaboration of this document, the information has been collected by the RTO associated to each demo-site, CIRCE for AMIII, TUBS for UPM and IKERLAN for TUPRAS.

The gathering and analysis of the data started during Task 2.1, where a questionnaire was developed and the technical visits to the different sites were realized. After this initial analysis of the waste streams to be used as fuel, the RTOs and the demo-sites continuous communication has allowed the complete characterization and evaluation of the potential use of the waste streams, advantages and disadvantages and other constraints.

Once the information was collected, each RTO send its corresponding report to CIRCE in order to obtain the consolidated version of the document.

The information collected in the report should be the baseline information for the DSS tools which will be developed in further working packages by N-SIDE.

4 AMIII DEMO-SITE

The steel manufacturing processes in the AMIII site produce some off-gases with a special interest to be used as fuels. In fact, these gases are currently used as fuel in different points of the plant or sold to external companies for steam and electricity generation.

However, AMIII is a consumer of natural gas, so the potential uses of these off-gases in other facilities or its use to increase the substitution ratio in the stages of the process where they are currently used has a great interest, in order to decrease, as much as possible, the natural gas consumption.

For the special case of the Asturias site, where the two plants of Gijón and Avilés are not connected via pipelines, the exploitation of the gases extracted from the processes must be performed on-site. The analysis of the potential off-gases for each plant is presented below.

4.1 Gijón plant waste streams to be valorised as fuels

Gijón facilities consists of a sintering plant, a blast furnace plant, a steel shop and three mills for wire, rail and heavy plate.

The coke used in the blast furnace comes from the Avilés plant, but it is planned to open the currently idled coke batteries installed in Gijón, so the scheme of the plant planned for 2020 is showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Fuels distribution for the AMIII Gijón plant (planned)

Within the Gijón plant, two potential streams off-gases will be available for their use as fuels for the different plant processes: Coke Oven Gas (COG) and Blast Furnace Gas (BFG).

4.1.1 Coke Oven Gas (COG)

Coke oven gas (COG) is produced during the coke-making process (carbonization of coal at high temperatures in an oxygen deficient atmosphere). Figure 2 shows a diagram of the Coke batteries where the COG is generated and properly washed.

Figure 2. Diagram of the Coke batteries

The coke-making process takes place in the coke batteries. Coke oven batteries consist on a group of ovens between of combustion chambers. There are some stacks that collect the fumes from the batteries and discharge them to the atmosphere. The temperature in the 4 stacks is around 245 °C. Coal feeding is made by a charging car that fills the combustion chamber from the top. Once charged, the coal is flattened, the chamber is sealed (top lids and front door) and the heating profile starts. Coal is heated to 1100 °C and during the pyrolysis process almost all the volatiles are eliminated leaving the coke as a final product. When the coke is out of the furnace in contact with air, it instantly ignites, so it must be quenched and cooled immediately up to 25 °C. The most extended procedure for the coke quenching is the intense irrigation watering which takes place in the coke-quenching tower. The irrigation water (T=25 °C) is evaporated when contacting with the coke at 1000 °C, resulting in clouds of steam which also contains dust, CO and H₂S. After the coke quenching, the coke is classified by sizes. The 30-60 mm sizes are sent to the blast furnace.

Figure 3. Coke oven batteries layout

From the batteries gas are obtained several by-products, the most important being the rich gas or COG. These gases are subjected to treatments for two reasons: to purify the rich gas by eliminating substances that would interfere in the distribution networks and to recover more valuable substances by themselves than as fuel.

Coke oven gas is formed during the coke production together with some other distillates such as tar among others. Firstly, the gas is cooled in the primary condenser and its temperature decreases from 80 °C to 30 °C. As a result of this first condensation is obtained tar as a by-product.

Then the COG is subjected to several treatments to recover the valuable by-products before using it as a fuel. The by-products facilities of the coke batteries include three different facilities, Benzol, ammonia sulphate and sulfuric acid fabrics. The benzol can be utilized as organic solvent in the chemical industry. The sulphate can be used as fertilizer. On the other hand, coal dust (coke fines) is the first by-product collected at the gas exit, they are used to inject pulverized coal directly in the blast furnace (PCI).

After the purifications carried out in the by-products facilities, part of the coke oven gas is reused in the same facility to introduce as a fuel in the combustion process, preheating it with steam until 40 °C. The rest is stored in gasholders to re-use as fuel in other facilities of the plant.

The raw coke gas coming from the coke batteries has a typical composition showed in Table 1.

Composition of Coke Oven Gas before washing [1]		
H ₂	36.1 - 61.7	%-vol.
CH ₄	15.7 - 27	%-vol.
N ₂	1.5 - 6	%-vol.
CO	3.4 - 5.8	%-vol.
CO ₂	1 - 5.4	%-vol.
C _n H _m	1.4 - 2.4	%-vol.
Sulphur total	100 - 800	mg/Nm ³
Lower heating value	9 - 10	MJ/Nm ³

Table 1. Usual composition and LHV of the Coke Oven Gas before washing

COG potential uses in Gijón plant comprise the use in the Sinter, in the Steel Shop or in the different mills, together with the use of about of the 50% which is consumed in the own cokemaking unit.

The advantages and disadvantages of the use of COG as fuel are defined in Table 2:

Table 2. Advantages and disadvantages of the use of COG as fuel

Advantages
COG has the highest heating value of all process gases, so the rate of substitution of NG is potentially high
COG is currently used mixed with natural gas for the Strip Mill in Avilés and in the past was used in the mills from Gijón, so the use of COG in some stages of the process is not new
Disadvantages
Investment must be made to transport the COG from the coke oven to the different furnaces and the furnaces adapted to be used with COG. Cleaning level could be a constrain (naphthalene, sulfhydic acid, ammonia, cyanides)

4.1.2 Blast Furnace Gas (BFG)

Blast Furnace Gas (BFG) is the gas generated as off-gas in the blast furnaces process (reduction with coke of iron ore to pig iron).

As seen in Figure 4, raw materials, composed of iron ore, fluxes, coke, and some ferroalloys whose main objective is the adjustment of pig iron composition, are charged at the top end of the furnace. Coke function is twofold, it is combustible as well as reductant agent, so, when coke is heated, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide are generated rising through the raw materials.

Figure 4. Blast furnace scheme

Therefore, within the blast furnace, a counter-flow process with chemical and thermal exchange is developed between the downward charge and the rising reductant gas. The reduction process is carried out by the carbon in this gas which is linked to the oxygen contained in the iron ore. Afterwards, the iron is combined with the carbon from coke in order to produce pig iron. In addition to pig iron, slag is generated as a sub-product which must be removed before the converter process.

Finally, there is a high volume of gas extracted on top (BFG) meanwhile pig iron with 3.5-4.5 % of carbon in composition and slag are extracted for the bottom part of the blast furnace. The volume inside the blast furnace is about 4000 m³ and the production can reach 10000 t/day.

The raw blast furnace gas is extracted at the top and cleaned in the gas cleaning system. For this, the gas pass through a vessel called "Dust Catcher" where undergoes an expansion, losing speed and consequently drag force, which cause the detachment of the heavier solid particles. The gas is then sent to a washing tower which removes the fine particles in suspension. The gas produced is BFG with low calorific value gas (due to the high volume of nitrogen in its composition).

Table 3 shows the usual composition and heating value of BFG (dry basis).

Table 3. Usual composition and LHV of the Blast Furnace Gas

Characteristics of Blast Furnace Gas [1]		
H ₂	1 - 8	%-vol.
N ₂	44 - 58	%-vol.
CO	19 - 27	%-vol.
CO ₂	16 - 26	%-vol.
Lower heating value	2.6 - 4	MJ/Nm ³

As shown in Figure 1, BFG is currently used to generate steam in the BFG boilers and it is used as fuel gas for the wire, rail and heavy plate mills. To be used in the mills, the BFG is mixed with NG in a proportion from 20% BFG up to 80% BFG. Besides, the BFG gas excess is sold to an external power plant (Aboño) to produce electricity.

The advantages and disadvantages of the BFG as fuel in Gijón plant are explained in Table 4:

Table 4. Advantages and disadvantages of the use of BFG as fuel

Advantages
BFG is currently used, so the needed infrastructure to transport the gas to some parts of the plant is already installed
The amount of BFG generated is so high that would be enough to cover all the energy needs of the plant
Disadvantages
The BFG low calorific value implies many disadvantages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The substitution rate can be small if the process requires a big amount of energy • The piping and other infrastructure (burners...) need to be adapted to transient high volumes of gas to cover the needs of energy of the furnaces • Some additional energy must be spent in order to reach enough combustion temperature when using BFG, i.e. heating the fuel and the combustion air

4.2 Avilés plant waste streams to be valorised as fuels

Regarding the plant of Avilés, the only residual fuel stream which will be exploited is the Converter Gas, also known as Basic Oxygen Furnace Gas (BOFG), produced during the basic oxygen steelmaking process that converts pig iron into steel.

4.2.1 Converter Gas (LDG or BOFG)

The gas recovery depends on different factors (O_2 blowing, amount of O_2 , amount of CO in the gas, Hot Metal Ratio etc). If the gas fulfils the conditions, it is sent to gasholder for its use and consumption in different sites from the steel shop. When the composition of the gas is not suitable, the gas is burned in the flare stack.

Basic Oxygen Furnace (BOF) is a vessel where the pig iron from blast furnace, scrap (which acts as refrigerant due to absorption of heat) and flux material, is refined into steel by injecting a jet of high-purity oxygen through the hot metal. More specifically, in a BOF the carbon content of pig iron, which is typically 4-5%, is reduced to varying levels below 1% depending on the product specifications, and unwanted impurities are removed.

Once the scrap and the pig iron are charged in the ladle, a tube, called lance, is inserted inside it and pure oxygen is injected through it, which oxidizes the excess carbon and other impurities present in the bath. Simultaneously to the oxygen blowing, the necessary fluxes (lime, dolomite and fluorspar) are sent from some hoppers, which will give rise to a slag that captures the formed compounds, thus preventing them from passing back to the steel.

To support the agitation of the bath and, therefore, the reactions in the converter, an inert gas, usually argon or nitrogen, is injected through the bottom of the ladle. This conversion process lasts approximately 15 minutes. About two minutes before the end of the process, a sub lance enters the converter, providing information on the composition and temperature, so that the corrections to achieve the desired product are made, if necessary.

The heat generated as well as its heat capacity are exploited from the fumes produced in the converter. Thus, the collection hood is a steam boiler where, at the expense of the heat given off in the cooling of the fumes, water vapor is obtained (see Figure 5).

The gas obtained after cooling and washing the fumes is sent, depending on whether its concentration in carbon monoxide (fuel gas) is high or low, to a gasometer for later use as fuel or to the chimney where it is burned.

The gas that is generated in the converter (900 °C after boiler) is subjected to a cleaning and cooling before being emitted. This cleaning is done in wet and consists of different phases:

- The first washing of the gas consists in the dosage of water through showers; this causes the expansion of the gas and the detachment of the heavier solid particles. The collection of finer particles begins even before through a shower of fines.
- After this phase the gas will pass through a droplet separator where the gas is centrifuged and there will be another dirty water collection point. Finally, the gas will pass to the outlet chimney through a wet-path electro filter and will undergo a final centrifugation.

Figure 5 . Converter gas treatment.

Table 5 shows the usual composition and lower heating value of this gas.

Table 5. Usual composition and LHV of the BOFG

Characteristics of the Converter Gas		
H ₂	0.9 - 1	%-vol.
N ₂	12 - 20	%-vol.
CO	58 - 70	%-vol.
CO ₂	15 - 20	%-vol.
O ₂	0.1 - 0.3	%-vol.
Lower heating value	6.6 - 10.1	MJ/Nm ³

Nowadays, the BOFG is sold to an external company, which uses it as fuel in engines for power generation and to generate steam in some boilers. The upcoming scenario will include the closure of this power station, so the BOFG will be used just to generate steam. This increases the interest of introducing this off-gas in some part of the process, to reduce the consumption of natural gas.

The advantages and disadvantages of BOFG are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Advantages and disadvantages of the use of BOFG as fuel

Advantages
BOFG is the second gas in terms of heating capacity in the steel industry (less than COG, more than BFG)
Disadvantages
BOFG availability is the lowest of all three off-gases
BOFG generation is discontinuous and its composition varying during the steelmaking process

4.3 Recovery, flexibility and valorisation potential in AMIII plants

As mentioned before, the use of these gases as fuel in the AMIII processes to substitute NG is currently implemented in the AMIII Asturias facilities. The challenge is to show how the novel strategies to be developed can lead to an increase of the substitution rate of the off-gases and therefore to a decrease in the consumption of NG. CFD simulations will help to theoretically characterize different off-gases blends under different conditions, and the advanced flame monitoring will allow controlling and assuring the proper combustion at every moment. Besides, the flexibility tools can help to optimise the use of these off-gases in according to some drivers, i.e. the economic benefit (considering investments, energy prices...).

Figure 6. Fuel energy streams in Gijón plant

In the case of Gijón plant, Figure 6 presents the diagram of the different gases used as fuel in the stages of the process. As shown, even though the amount of BFG generated would cover the energy needs of the whole plant, its use is currently limited. The properties of the gas generated, with a low calorific value, make necessary additional actions in the gas, like preheating the air/fuel or mixing it with natural gas.

The reopening of the idled coke oven batteries from Gijón will make available an important amount of COG, which can potentially be used as fuel in the sintering line or in the different mill furnaces. However, this will require some investments in order to adapt the piping and the furnaces and flexibility tools that will be developed during BAMBOO project can help to make the right decision.

Figure 7. Fuel energy streams in Avilés plant

For Avilés, Figure 7, the production of off-gases is more limited, especially after the planned closure of the coke oven batteries, which are currently producing COG. COG is used in two ways: to produce steam and as fuel for the reheating furnaces of the hot strip mill, mixed with natural gas.

Besides, in Avilés plant, there is an agreement with an external company to which the steel gases (Coke Oven Gas or Basic Oxygen Furnace Gas) are sold. This company, in turn, uses a certain amount of these gases to produce electricity and other part is used in its boilers to produce steam. Due to this agreement, when the boilers fuel is provided by ArcelorMittal, the steam cost is low.

On the other hand, the Coke Plant in Avilés should be shut-down, once the revamped installation in Gijón is in operation. That makes that the energy requirement in Avilés should be provided mainly by NG. In terms of flexibility, the interest lies in the potential use of BOFG to decrease the natural gas in the different parts of the process. Furthermore, any production of steam by waste heat will allow to allocate BOFG to heating requirements (i.e. less NG consumption).

5 UPM DEMO-SITE

The UPM site in Plattling produces around 600.000 t of coated (LWC) and uncoated (SC) paper per year. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show an overview of the Plattling site, including the waste-water treatment plant, which was defined as the main focus in the early stage of the project.

The raw materials used for paper production are **wood pulp**, **chemical pulp** and **deinked pulp**.

The wood pulp is produced either in continuous or in pressure grinders. The raw material used is wood, mainly harvested from the regional forest. Unsuitable fibre components are sorted out in the sorting stage. In the bleaching stage groundwood is bleached with hydrogen peroxide and, if necessary, with hydrosulphite to achieve the required whiteness.

Chemical pulp is purchased from external producers. After dissolving it in water in the pulp processing stage, it can be used without further bleaching.

Deinked pulp is produced on-site from different types of waste paper. In the recycling facility waste paper is defibrated in the pulper. The printing inks are removed and discharged in flotation tanks.

Wood pulp, chemical pulp and deinked pulp are processed into paper in the **two paper machines** with additive materials (retention agents, fixing agents, shading colours, etc.) and fillers (carbonate, kaolin). For the production of coated paper, the paper machine is supplemented by a coating machine, where a layer of coating pigments (calcium carbonate, kaolin) is applied to the paper.

5.1 Plattling mill waste streams to be valorised as fuels

The **waste-water treatment plant** serves to purify the waste-water from the production and ancillary plants before discharging it into the Isar river. The waste-water treatment plant at UPM Plattling consists of two aerobic biological stages. First, the waste-water flow is hydraulically homogenised in an upstream buffer (waste-water tower). Waste-water is then fed into the mechanical pre-treatment system (primary clarifier), where the solid content is separated through sedimentation. The primary sludge, also called mechanical sludge is removed from the bottom of the sedimentation tanks.

Through cooling towers, a suitable temperature for the biological treatment is reached. After cooling, waste-water is fed into tanks ventilated with compressed air, for the biological degradation of the organic substances. In the final sedimentation (final clarifier) the biological excess sludge is separated by sedimentation. If required, two tertiary treatment stages (flotation and ozone/bio-filter plant) are available for further purification of waste-water. The treated waste-water is discharged into the Isar river through a pipeline.

Figure 8. Overview of UPM Plattling site

Figure 9. Overview of the waste-water treatment plant

Three types of sludge residuals are produced during the purification process: **primary sludge**, **bio-sludge** and **deinking sludge**.

The primary sludge produced in the preliminary clarification is dewatered in a screw press with the addition of flocculants. The average dry content after dewatering is about 50%. The main components of the dewatered primary sludge are wood, deinked pulp and cellulose fibres as well as fillers and pigments (calcium carbonate and kaolin). This sludge can be recycled as porosity agent in brick production.

The biological excess sludge (bio-sludge) produced in the final clarification is dewatered via a pre-screening bench and a twine wire press. About 24.000 t of bio-sludge are produced and disposed every year in Plattling. To improve dewatering, small amounts of fibre and flocculants are added to the bio-sludge. The average dry content after dewatering is about 28%. The essential components of the dewatered bio-sludge are biomass from the biological purification stages and small amounts of wood/waste paper fibres and pigments. Bio-sludge is disposed and can be employed for the production of fertilizer or co-incineration.

The deinking sludge produced during waste paper processing in the recycling facility is dewatered in a screw press. It contains sorted, unusable fibre components of the waste paper and the ink

particles removed by flotation. The dry content is around 50%. Deinked sludge can also be recycled as porosity agent in brick production.

The residual particles (plastics, metal, etc.) contained in the waste paper are sorted out at the beginning of the waste paper preparation process and dewatered in a screw press.

In Table 7 the compositions of bio-sludge, primary sludge, deinking sludge and other residual particles at the UPM site in Plattling are listed.

Table 7. Usual composition of bio-sludge, primary sludge, deinking sludge and other residual particles

	Bio-sludge	Primary sludge	Deinking sludge	Other residual particles	
Dry matter	22,9	52,0	48,2	30,0	%
Moisture content	77,1	48,0	51,8	70,0	%
Ash content (550°C)	35,5	60,6	42,0	16,3	%-vol.
Ash content (950°C)	25,3	43,1	36,2	15,9	%-vol.
Carbon (total)	32,6	30,2	31,5	46,5	%-vol.
Organic carbon	31,0	28,3	29,9	42,6	%-vol.
Inorganic carbon	1,60	1,90	1,60	3,9	%-vol.
Nitrogen (total)	3,5	<0,20	<0,10	<0,10	%-vol.
Hydrogen	4,56	3,08	1,59	5,93	%-vol.
Oxygen	23,1	6,01	24,9	31,2	%-vol.
Calorific value	2.700-3.800	4.800-6.000	4.500-5.600	5.400-8.700	kJ/kg
Lower heat value	640-1800	3.000-4.600	2.900-4.000	3.500-6.800	kJ/kg

The main focus of UPM within the project is the development of a drying facility, aiming at reducing the moisture content of bio-sludge and thus valorising its potential to be used as fuel in other paper mills owned by UPM. The key-factor in the development of the new drying equipment is the minimization of drying costs, which should be lower than the current sludge disposal cost.

Within BAMBOO, UPM will design and install the novel drying facility and will assess different options to use the dried sludge.

As shown in Figure 10, primary sludge and bio-sludge are treated separately in the sludge treatment plant in Plattling. Primary sludge is pressed in a screw press and then disposed as solid waste.

The quantity of excess bio-sludge depends on the amount of paper produced, the desired paper brightness, the required peroxide demand for wood bleaching and the chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the biological treatment. With the aim of optimizing the biological stage, the solid content of bio-sludge should be kept as constant as possible in the aeration tank, thus a certain amount of excess bio-sludge must be continuously removed. Bio-sludge is characterized by a high organic content and has typically poor dewatering properties. In order to increase the dewatering rate of bio-sludge, a small amount of primary sludge is conveyed to the excess sludge tank as dewatering aid, where it is mixed to bio-sludge. The sludge mixture is dewatered in a twin wire press, currently able to increase the dry matter (DM) from 10 to 28%. After dewatering, bio-sludge is then stored in silos before being disposed.

Because of its organic content, bio-sludge has the potential to be valorised as fuel. The sludge heat value depends on its dry content: the lower the moisture content, the higher the heat value.

Figure 10. Sludge flows in the current configuration

Figure 11: Bio-sludge flows in the target configuration

Figure 11 illustrates the planned configuration to be achieved throughout the project. UPM is planning to build a drying facility aiming at a further reduction of the embedded moisture content in bio-sludge and consequently of its storage volume. The storage silos for dewatered sludge have a low capacity, making the sludge disposal necessary on daily basis. Because of the low capacity of the silos, the dewatering process has a relatively low flexibility. In the target configuration, the existing silo for dewatered sludge storage will be modified and one additional silo for dried sludge will be installed, increasing the flexibility rate for disposal.

Second-use possibilities for dried bio-sludge include incineration, landfilling, production of fertilizer or fuel substitution. The last option is the preferred one within the aim of BAMBOO. A pelletizer will be hence installed within the sludge drier, facilitating the transport of dried-sludge to other production facilities and enhancing its valorisation potential.

In Table 8, the advantages and drawbacks of using bio-sludge as fuel are highlighted.

Table 8. Advantages and disadvantages of the use of bio-sludge as fuel

Advantages
UPM is currently paying a disposal cost for bio-sludge. The installation of the drying equipment would enhance its potential to be used as fuel in other production plants and reduce the disposal cost
The drying facility will be operated using a bivalent supply operation, including recovered waste-water heat from the production plant
Disadvantages
The drying equipment implies high investments for the paper mill, as well as operation and maintenance costs. A thorough evaluation must be therefore carried out
As dried sludge won't be valorised on the same site where it is produced, transportation costs and its environmental impact represent possible drawbacks
Dried bio-sludge has a lower calorific value compared to other organic fuels

5.2 Recovery, flexibility and valorisation potential at UPM

At this stage of the project, relevant questions to be answered concern the design and operation of the sludge drier:

- Where should the drier be installed?
- Which technology could be used to dry bio-sludge?
- Which heat sources are more feasible for the drier?
- When is it more convenient to dry bio-sludge?
- How can the dried sludge be valorised?
- What is the target dry content in bio-sludge?

The most suitable location to install the drier is the building of the waste-water treatment plant, where the existing dewatering system is located. The drying equipment will be hence placed in proximity of the press.

Different technologies for the drying process are under evaluation and will be assessed in WP7.

The flexibility potential of UPM resides mainly in the operation of the sludge drying system. The drier will be operated with two different energy sources, e.g. recovered waste-heat from the production plant, or as an alternative saturated steam, and electricity either from the combined heat and power plant (CHP) or from the grid, to operate the heat pumps. Different scenarios for waste heat recovery and energy flexibility will be simulated in WP6. The DSS tool will support the decisions related to the drier operation. The additional installation of a power to heat boiler within the drying system, to support the power grid stability, is no longer part of the investment plan.

The selected waste-heat stream is waste-water from the grinding process in the first production unit. The main focus within BAMBOO is the installation of heat exchangers and heat pumps to supply the drier with thermal energy. Details related to the supply scheme as well as a thorough characterization of waste heat streams can be found in D2.4 *Definition of specifications and data requirements for waste heat recovery analysis*.

Since the CHP plant, supplying the paper mill in Plattling, already has a good efficiency rate, dried bio-sludge is not planned to be valorised on-site as fuel, but to be rather sold to the market or used as fuel in another paper mill, where it could substitute recovered wood. In order to estimate the substitution rate and the combustion properties of dried sludge as well as the resulting emissions, CFD simulations will be performed by CIRCE in the course of the project. Other valorisation routes for dried bio-sludge will be further evaluated.

The dry content to be reached after drying is 90%.

6 TUPRAS DEMO-SITE

Izmir refinery, Figure 12, which started production in 1972 with an annual crude oil processing capacity of 3 million tons, is now registered as having an annual refining capacity of 11.9 million tons following significant capacity increases and unit modernizations carried out over the years.

Figure 12. Picture of Tüpras Izmir refinery

The refinery's production of main marketable petroleum products - consisting of LPG, naphtha, gasoline, jet fuel, diesel, base oil, heating oil, fuel oil, bitumen, wax, extracts and other products - reached to 10.6 million tons. Izmir Refinery has a 400 thousand tons capacity base oil production unit, the only one of its kind in Turkey. In 2017, the Izmir Refinery achieved sales of 10.7 million tons, of which 7.6 million tons were sold domestically.

6.1 Izmir refinery waste streams to be valorised as fuels

The recovery of off-gases and other waste oils for internal reuse as fuels is a common procedure in the oil refining industries and can account for up to 59% of the fuel usage of the plant fuel use [2]. As described in D2.2 (*Report on material and energy flow characterisation on plant and relevant process level*) mass and thermal integration within a refinery process is quite high. Particularly regarding waste gas streams (see Figure 13; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la**

referencia.), all the gas effluents from the different processing units are directed to the Gas Processing Unit where they are further converted to additional finished products. As an outcome of this processing some fuel gases are produced which are used as refinery fuel to provide the thermal energy required by the various processing units (usually by burning that fuel in boilers to produce steam, which is then used as the heating medium in the units).

Figure 13. Refinery process off-gases and their current re-use

It should be pointed that not all gas streams in Figure 13 are waste streams, but rather inputs to other processes. For example, hydrotreating units are used to remove some undesirable components (mainly sulphur, but also nitrogen) from the different distillates coming out of the atmospheric distillation column. For this purpose, hydrogen gas is fed to the hydrotreaters and the resulting gas is a mixture of unreacted hydrogen and hydrogen sulfide (H_2S). This gas stream is sweetened by removing the sulphur (which can be another product of the refinery) and the clean gas is mainly recycled back to the hydrotreater [3]. Thus, just a small fraction of the gas stream (some purge gas after the sweetening process) is actually available for being used as a fuel. On the other hand, other units, such as for example the naphtha catalytic reformer, are net hydrogen producers, and this excess is used to feed the hydrotreating units [4].

As a result of the high number of refinery units present in an oil refinery, multiple fuel gas streams are produced at distributed sites in the process. These streams can be used either locally (in or close to the unit where they have been generated) or blended to form what is known as refinery fuel gas (RFG), which is then used as fuel in boilers and process heaters throughout the refinery. RFG is typically a blend of gas streams produced as by-products in various refinery units including catalytic reforming, hydrotreating and hydrocracking, catalytic cracking, and coking. On a dry basis, major components in RFG can consist of percent levels of numerous hydrocarbons (C_1 - C_6+ , saturated and unsaturated), hydrogen (H_2), carbon oxides (CO and CO_2), nitrogen (N_2), and possibly some oxygen (O_2). Saturated hydrocarbons in RFG come from catalytic reforming, hydrotreating, hydrocracking, and the like; unsaturated arise from such refining processes as catalytic cracking and coking [5].

The amount of certain species in RFG (such as hydrogen sulphide), as well as the lack of a close to refinery nearby market for this fuel makes it no attractive product to be sold even with discount rates. That is why the present approach is to use it internally for the refinery process heating needs.

Thus, from the above description there can be concluded that not much room for valorising waste streams as fuels exists in Tüpras processes. However, a deeper analysis is proposed to evaluate the alternative uses of this waste fuel gases to consider their flexibility potential for producing additional valuable products from them.

6.2 Recovery, flexibility and valorisation potential at TÜPRAS

As mentioned before, RFG is a combination of refinery unit waste or by-product gases, often referred to as off-gases. The off-gases that are sent to the RFG pool are those that cannot be processed elsewhere in the refinery either because of the composition or because there is an excess available. The off gases in the RFG come from various refinery unit operations (catalytic reforming, FCC, hydrotreating, coking) and their availability and amount will depend on the refinery operation. Hydrogen-containing off-gases may be partly or fully used in hydrogen-consuming units or may be treated to recover the hydrogen in a membrane or PSA unit so that a hydrogen lean gas is available to the RFG pool. Also, off-gases or off-gas blends with high olefin levels may be treated to recover olefins, with the olefin lean gas going to the RFG pool. Thus, RFG can differ significantly between refineries. Examples of RFGs, which have been proposed for

hydrogen plant feeds, are shown in Table 9. This shows the substantial variations in hydrogen, from 11-35 mol%; methane, from 26-65 mol%; and olefins, from 2.6-15.9 mol% [6].

Table 9. RFG compositions for various sources

RFG compositions considered for hydrogen plant feed						
Mol%	Example 1	Example 2	Example 3	Example 4	Example 5	Example 6
Hydrogen	34.9	10.8	25.5	34.1	13.9	14.4
Methane	26.3	64.9	34.8	45.3	43.2	42.3
Ethane	11.0	13.4	23.5	8.2	12.2	13.7
Propane	9.5	2.5	5.2	3.2	8.3	6.8
Butanes	7.1	1.4	3.2	1.4	0.3	4.4
Pentanes	0.0	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.3	1.5
Hexanes	0.0	0.3	0.9	0.2	0.3	0.6
Ethene	3.8	3.1	3.4	1.5	7.2	6.6
Propene	2.1	0.5	0.6	0.9	8.3	6.7
Butenes	3.0	~	~	0.2	0.3	0.3
Pentenes	0.0	~	~	~	0.1	Trace
Nitrogen	1.9	1.8	1.9	3.7	4.5	2.2
Argon	~	~	~	Trace	Trace	~
Oxygen	Trace	~	~	~	~	~
Carbon monoxide	~	0.3	0.3	0.3	1.1	Trace
Carbon dioxide	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	~	0.5

As can be seen from the compositions above, hydrogen is the main volumetric component of RFG. This high H₂ concentration means a low volumetric heating value, which in turn leads to high gas velocities in combustion systems designed to operate with other common fuels (e.g. natural gas), eventually saturating fuel gas valves [7]. Removing hydrogen from this RFG could have a double benefit, first by avoiding this saturation problem and second by reducing the current hydrogen production plant duty.

On the other hand, hydrogen is gaining attention as an alternative fuel for transportation, where the market price could make any recovery scheme attractive enough to place an investment. The most common paths for hydrogen production considered in the studies (steam methane reforming and water electrolysis) reflects cost of production in the order of few euros per kg of H₂ [8]. If recovery of hydrogen from RFG is feasible at lower cost, it would set up the floor for an additional marketable product of refineries that will open additional flexibility in their operation.

Depending on the technology considered for extracting hydrogen from the RFG (e.g. cryogenic technology, pressure swing adsorption, membrane technology) [9], the cost and the technical challenges can be different, and a deeper analysis should be performed in order to assess if the cost of this recovery approach match the cost of the other hydrogen production techniques currently considered for market hydrogen production. Anyway, recovery of hydrogen from off-gases was already considered before by TÜPRAS. However, with the state of the art, it turns out that the recovery process is not feasible.

In Table 10, the advantages and drawbacks of using RFG as fuel are highlighted.

Table 10. Advantages and disadvantages of the use of RFG

Advantages
Removing hydrogen from RFG is possible and could have a double benefit: first avoiding saturation problem in fuel gas valves and second reducing the current hydrogen production plant duty.
Hydrogen production from RFG may set up the floor for an additional marketable product of refineries.
Disadvantages
Low volumetric heating value and high gas velocities in combustion systems designed to operate with other common fuels.
Different cost and technical challenges depending on the technology considered for extracting hydrogen from the RFG.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This document analyses the potential waste streams in the demo-sites of AMIII, UPM and TÜPRAS which can be valorised as fuel. The collection of the data performed by the RTOs in conjunction with the demo-sites has allowed to have a detailed characterization of these off-process products in the steel, paper and petrochemical sectors and to know the advantages and disadvantages of the use of these streams to replace traditional fossil fuels.

In the case of AMIII and UPM, the information will be used in the WP5 and WP6 of the BAMBOO project, as input for the development of combustion models which will be used for the DSS tool. For AMIII, the future goal is to extend the current use of these gases in other parts of the steel production process, replacing fossil fuels as natural gas. In the case of UPM, the target is the valorisation of the bio-sludge to be sold as fuel or to be used in other mills.

Most of the TÜPRAS refineries off-gases are currently valorised internally as combustion fuels for internal heaters and furnaces, so with this operation scheme there is no flexibility option from waste fuels. Nevertheless, the information collected can help in exploring potential alternative uses for RFGs with economic value that could open the opportunity to operate refineries with flexibility regarding the fuels used internally. This analysis will help to the replicability of the BAMBOO results in the petrochemical sectors.

8 NOMENCLATURE

AOP	Advanced oxidation process
BFG	Blast furnace gas
BOFG	Basic oxygen furnace gas
CFD	Computer fluid dynamics
CHP	Combined heat and power plant
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
COG	Coke oven gas
DM	Dry matter
DSS	Decision support system
LDG	Linz-Donawitz converter gas
LHV	Lower heating value
LPG	Liquefied petroleum gas
LWC	Lightweight coated paper
MBBR	Moving bed biofilm reactor
NG	Natural gas
PCI	Pulverized coal injection
RFG	Refinery Fuel Gas
RTO	Research and technology organisation
SC	Semi coated paper

9 REFERENCES

- [1] "Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document for Iron and Steel Production" 2013.
- [2] "Waste fuels are a significant energy source for U.S. manufacturers":
<https://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=13531>
- [3] Hydrogen Processes in Refineries, Hydrodesulfurization (HDS):
https://www.fkit.unizg.hr/_download/repository/PRPP_2013_Refinig_intro_H2_tech.pdf
- [4] Catalytic reforming: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Catalytic_reforming
- [5] Study examines use of refinery fuel gas for hydrogen production, Oil & Gas Journal, June 25, 2007
- [6] Refinery fuel gas in steam reforming hydrogen plants,
www.digitalrefining.com/article/1000351
- [7] Improving Refinery Fuel Gas Composition:
http://www.refinerlink.com/blog/Improving_Refinery_Fuel_Gas_Composition/
- [8] Hydrogen market penetration feasibility assessment: Mobility and natural gas markets in the US, Europe, China and Japan, International journal of hydrogen energy 44 (2019), 16048-16068
- [9] Hydrogen Recovery from Refinery Off-gases, Journal of Applied Sciences 5(3) · March 2005

